

Cognitive Load Questionnaire

[Additional information on the wearable device]

Take approximately one minute to sit quietly with as little movement as possible and relax with your eyes closed. Then proceed with your normal working day tasks. Please document what type of task you are doing (e.g. coding, debugging, coffee break etc.), the start and end time of each task and the cognitive load you experienced during the time of the task. Cognitive load is the amount of mental processing you require to perform a task. Please rate your cognitive load at the end of every task.

Task	Cognitive Load Rating						Start time	End time
	Very low					Very high		
Baseline recording								
Baseline recording								

At the end of your work day, please take one minute to sit quietly with as little movement as possible and relax with your eyes closed.

[Additional information on the wearable device and how the study further proceeds]

Thank you very much for participating in this study!